

Assessment of Pathogenic Microbial Presence In Ground Water At Sreepur Sub-district, Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

A total of 30 groundwater samples were gathered within the vicinity of the Sreepur sub-district in the Gazipur District in Bangladesh, during July 2023. These samples were collected from different locations in the Sreepur sub-district. The assessment of groundwater indicated its suitability for both drinking and irrigation purposes. On the other hand, surface water quality exhibited variations depending on the specific sampling sites and water origins. Among the samples obtained from surface water, noteworthy observations included the highest concentration of Gram-positive bacterial count found in water sourced from the MC Bazar, measuring 112 cfu/ml, followed by the Chatir Bazar, Mawna, and others with 101 cfu/ml. The contamination of the MC Bazar and Chatir Bazar was attributed to the discharge of domestic water from residences. The potential ramifications of pollution progression in the smaller area of Gazipur District could profoundly impact the environment and human health in the times ahead. However, we found deadly pathogenic bacteria in the groundwater of sreepur, Gazipur which is alarming. Consequently, there is a strong call for a comprehensive and detailed assessment of this situation.

Keywords: Microbial Ratio, Pathogenic Microbial Presence, Groundwater Sreepur, Water test

INTRODUCTION

Vast volumes of subterranean water, predominantly drawn from shallow aquifers, serve as the primary source of potable water in Bangladesh. Due to the absence of adequately treated water, people heavily rely on this groundwater. Ensuring the ongoing integrity of irrigation systems and livelihoods hinges on effective water quality management, which profoundly influences soil attributes. Evaluation of drinking water places significant emphasis on both the chemical and physical attributes of the water. The presence of various microorganisms significantly influences the safety and appropriateness of groundwater, impacting its toxicity or suitability. Common pathogenic microorganisms found in drinking water encompass e-coli, coliforms, and legionella. The assessment of drinking water quality is typically predicated upon key criteria such as the ratio of bacterial presence and the prevalence of heavy metals. Furthermore, additional indicators, including the magnesium adsorption ratio (MAR), Kelly's ratio (KR), total hardness (TH), permeability index (PI), and residual sodium bicarbonate (RSBC), ought to be taken into consideration to classify groundwater. This study was conducted within the Sreepur sub-district, located in the Gazipur District of Bangladesh. The presence of detrimental pathogenic bacteria characterizes instances of depression. Inhabitants of this district are pioneers in utilizing both shallow and deep tube wells for their drinking water needs.

To ensure the enduring viability of groundwater resources, continual monitoring of water quality is imperative. Bearing this in mind, an endeavor was undertaken to assess the groundwater quality within the Sreepur sub-district. This analysis sought to ascertain the precise extent of pathogenic microorganisms, particularly focusing on the fitness of the water for consumption. Groundwater is the principal source of drinking water in Bangladesh, and there has been a remarkable surge in its extraction. The attributes of drinking water that appear most pivotal in determining its quality are now discussed.

- (1) temperature,
- (2) dissolved oxygen,
- (3) pH level,
- (4) total dissolved solids,
- (5) conductivity,
- (6) suspended sediment,
- (7) nutrients,
- (8) metals
- (9) hydrocarbons,
- (10) industrial chemicals level and
- (11) microbial presence limit.

Approximately 41% of the population in Bangladesh is currently devoid of access to clean potable water, as reported by the Daily Star on April 26, 2023. Mridha et al. (1996) have documented that groundwater sources contribute to roughly 70% of irrigation water and 90% of the total potable water supply in Bangladesh. The significance of groundwater as a source of drinking water has undergone notable transformations. From 1982/83 to 1996/97, the proportion of groundwater contribution to the overall irrigated land escalated from 41% to 71%. Subsequently, this proportion exceeded 75% by 2001 (Ali, 2003). Given that groundwater serves as the sole constraining factor for further intensification of hydration,

ensuring its judicious usage in terms of both quality and quantity remains imperative (Sarkar and Hasan, 2006).

Shahidullah et al. (2000) conducted a study aimed at evaluating the quality of groundwater within a specific region of Bangladesh, focusing on the Phulpur Upazila in the Mymensingh district. The research involved the analysis of water samples obtained from 14 deep tube wells, with a focus on parameters such as SAR, SSP, and RSC. The findings of their investigation indicated the absence of salinity and toxicity concerns in relation to irrigation water, thereby affirming the suitability of groundwater for sustained irrigation purposes. However, certain wells demonstrated inadequacies for both irrigation and drinking applications due to elevated levels of Fe concentration, total dissolved solids (TDS), and pH values. Among the factors governing water quality, the researchers identified a linear correlation between SSP and SAR.

Quddus and Zaman (1996) delved into the examination of irrigation water quality within selected villages of the Meherpur district in Bangladesh. Their analysis highlighted the presence of prominent ions such as calcium, magnesium, sodium, bicarbonate, sulfate, and chloride, with minor traces of other ions including potassium, carbonate, nitrate, iron, boron, and silica. While some ions demonstrated potential benefits, excessive amounts of certain ions were linked to adverse effects on crop growth and soil attributes.

Talukder et al. (1998) carried out analogous research in Kishoreganj, where their findings emphasized that irrigation employing subpar-quality water resulted in diminished soil productivity, alterations in soil chemistry and physics, crop toxicity, and ultimately reduced yields. Despite their observations, they concurred with the notion that the groundwater's quality did not align with standards suitable for consumption.

Sarkar and Hasan (2006) undertook an investigation into the water quality of a groundwater basin in Bangladesh, evaluating its appropriateness for both irrigation and drinking purposes. Their analytical results demonstrated that the composition of groundwater samples generally adhered to acceptable levels for irrigation applications, with the exception of elevated Cl⁻ values that contributed to issues of toxicity. Standard indices for assessing water quality parameters, including pH, EC, SAR, SSP, RSBC, MAR, PI, KR, and TH, were found to fall within permissible ranges.

Study area

Sreepur Upazila with an area of 560.76 sq km is bounded by Gazipur and Maymensingh district. (Fig. 1). The present research was conducted during the period of January 2023 to June 2023 in the microbiology laboratory of the prime pharmaceuticals limited. The samples (deep groundwater) were collected from Mawna, MC Bazar, Jayna Bazar, Brindabon, and other areas of the Sreepur of Gazipur district (Figure 1) and transported through ice flasks to the laboratory for isolation, identification, biochemical and antibiogram characterization.

A total of 30 samples were collected from source water and brought to the laboratory of Prime Pharmaceuticals Limited through cool chain maintenance. After that, the samples were inoculated into the Nutrient broth for better nourishment of the desirable organisms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Several microbiological tests were performed for the confirmation of the isolates of pathogens. The microbiological tests performed as gram staining, isolation test, and membrane filtration.

The microbiological test was performed according to the method described by “Tim Sendle - Pharmaceutical Microbiology (2016)” and “H. Kussmaul - Encyclopedia of Food Sciences and Nutrition (Second Edition) (2003). Before performing the test, a pure culture of the pathogens was allowed to grow in nutrient broth. One drop of cultured broth was placed on the cover slip and placed inverted over the concave depression of the hanging drop slide to make hanging drop preparation. Vaseline was used around the concave depression of the hanging drop slide for better attachment of the cover slip to prevent airflow and evaporation of the fluid. The hanging drop slide was then examined carefully under 100x the objective of a compound microscope using immersion oil. The motile and non-motile organisms were differentiated by observing motility in contrast with the to-and-fro movement of bacteria.

A suspension of the test organism was prepared in nutrient broth by overnight culture for 72 hours at 37°C. The broth was streaked using by sterile glass spreader homogenously on the medium. Pieces of equipment have been applied aseptically to the surface of the inoculated plates at an appropriate special arrangement with the help of sterile forceps on agar plates. The plates were then inverted and incubated at 37°C for 72 hours. A sterile glass spreader was used to spread the

culture homogenously on the medium. After incubation, the plates were examined.
(Table 1)

Serial No.	Media	Plate No	Total Colony Count	Detected Bacteria	Responsible for Disease
01	Soyaben Casine Digest Agar	1	1280	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	1. Bloodstream infections, 2. Pneumonia, 3. Bone and joint infections.
		2	1472		
02	Macconkey Agar	1	2600	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	1. Urinary tract infections 2. Diarrhea
		2	2860	<i>E.coli</i>	
03	Mannitol Salt Agar	1	23	<i>Staphylococcus haemolyticus</i>	1. Native valve endocarditis, 2.Sepsis peritonitis 3. urinary tract wound 4. Bone and joint infections
		2	25		
04	Xylose Lysine Deoxycholate Agar	1	4	<i>Salmonella enterica</i>	1. Fever 2. Abdominal pain 3. Diarrhea 4. Nausea
		2	5		
05	Cetrimide Agar	1	3190	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	1. Eye Infection 2. Osteomyelitis 3. Septicemia 4. Meningitis
		2	3240	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1. Pneumonia

Table - 1

During the experiment, it was necessary to preserve the isolated microorganism for a longer period. The preservation isolates in pure culture form were stored in sterile 80% glycerin and were used as stock culture. The equal volume of 80% glycerin and bacterial culture were mixed and capped tightly and stored at -70 °C. The isolated organisms were given code names for convenience. This process has been cited in the reference (1).

Results

The results of the cultural, morphological, and motility characteristics of the isolates are presented in Table (1). Among all of the isolates obtained from this study *E. coli* produced turbidity from the line of inoculation in Motility Indole Urea media (MIU).

The organisms were checked and confirmed by their purity using selected media. Then they were grown in nutrient broth for biochemical tests. For identification, a series of selective biochemical tests for *E. coli* were performed with the culture. All the isolated organisms fermented five sugars Dextrose, Sucrose, Fructose, Glucose, and Maltose produced acid with gas. Acid production was indicated by the color change from reddish to orange-yellow color and the gas production was manifested by the appearance of gas bubbles in the inverted Durham's tubes. All the isolates of *E. coli* were found positive in catalase, Methyl-red test, Indole test, and VP test negative.

This study was aimed at the isolation, identification, and biochemical differentiation of pathogens from the groundwater collected from several locations of Sreepur, Gazipur district, and Antibioqram characterization of desirable microorganisms was also accomplished. Most of the source water was direct from Tube-well water while the two sources were stored local submersible water pump. Only of 30 sample source, did we detect pathogenic microbial presence in every sample.

Isolation and identification results of the study also indicated that the field sample contained Gram negative, rod shape, and motile organisms with various colony characteristics (large, smooth, round, and sticky) in different bacteriological media. The colony characteristics of the isolated *E. coli* in different media resemble the colony characteristics of *E. coli* as stated by Escherich (1885) and Ali et al. (1998).

The fermentation reaction by the isolates of *E. coli* in five basic sugars (dextrose, sucrose, fructose, maltose, and mannitol) and in dulcitol was positive. More over, MR reaction and Catalase tests were also positive for *E. coli*. The organism was able to ferment lactose, dextrose mannitol, sucrose, and maltose completely. The result of sugar fermentation agreed with the findings of Beutin et al. (1997) and Sandhu et al. (1996). These respective authors reported that although *E. coli* ferments all five basic sugars it partially fermented sucrose and maltose. Variations in the results might be due to genetic factors and the nature of the inhabitants of the organisms.

E. coli was isolated and characterized successfully from Sreepur of Gazipur district in Bangladesh using different cultural, morphological examination, biochemical, and antimicrobial susceptibility test. Further molecular studies on the isolated *E. coli* strains will be required for a better understanding of their clonality and mechanisms of antimicrobial resistance.

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